

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

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D8.1. GI-NI's findings on future challenges, policies and governance options for shared prosperity and change

Report and stakeholder input: Challenges, actors and policies

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Summary

This report builds on the work of the GI-NI project and feeds into new upcoming work (D8.2 and D8.3). It starts by taking stock of the key empirical findings pertinent to the transformations at the core of the project: technological transformation, globalisation, and migration, central to WP3-5. These findings are then cross-referenced with the insights gleaned from the foresight exercise, as outlined in WP7.

The purpose of this report is to examine the role of the EU. First, focusing on its external dimension as a global actor, which by operating in the global context can influence these pivotal transformations. Second on the internal dimension, as regulator of the EU single market, supplier of normative common values and funds, which can enhance their positive socioeconomic impacts or mitigate the negative ones.

Irrespective of the specific scenario that unfolds, as defined in D7.3, the EU will face substantial challenges. Recent events, including the conflict in Ukraine and escalating tensions between China and the US, have created an unfavourable global landscape for the EU. The mounting pressure to compete for technological supremacy, primarily driven by the US and China, presents a considerable hurdle. Moreover, historical EU prosperity rooted in openness and free trade faces threats, posing a significant risk to the EU's economic model. Against the backdrop of these evolving trends and a potential worsening of circumstances, the EU is reassessing its stance, with the concepts of strategic autonomy and economic security taking centre stage in EU deliberations. These shifts are redefining the EU's role as a global actor and possibly lead to a renewed approach to international cooperation and policy actions.

Furthermore, ongoing labour market transitions catalysed by technological advancements are anticipated to result in worker displacement, job realignment, and, in the short term, job losses in certain sectors. Conversely, some industries may encounter challenges in securing workers with requisite skills. Even under the most favourable scenario, significant labour market challenges are anticipated, necessitating policy intervention to mitigate such impacts. Similarly, inequality is unlikely to reduce as a market outcome. This implies that there is a need for policies to mitigate inequality. The capacity, both in terms of resources and political capital, to implement such policies will depend on the available resources. The report identifies multiple national and sub-national actors, public and private, that with

their tools can play a role in this context and outlines various policy measures that can be employed.

1. Introduction

The GI-NI research seeks to comprehensively grasp how three major transformations, technological progress, globalisation, and migration, can impact inequality and labour market outcomes. It also aims to formulate policies and governance strategies to tackle future EU challenges and to improve the distribution of opportunities.

Against these objectives, this report aims to bring together different parts of the GI-NI research, which can contribute to shaping forward-looking policies for the EU, put them into perspective in the future defined by the foresight analysis, and focus on the role that different actors play in shaping it.

As will be illustrated, the main focus is on two of the three transformations, technological progress and globalisation, and the role that the EU plays at two levels associated with its external and internal dimensions, respectively. In the global context, the EU, as a global actor, can contribute to shaping the trajectories of globalisation and technological transformation and hence affect their socio-economic impacts. Within the EU, the EU, together with other actors, both private and public, national and local, can contribute to responding to and mitigating the socio-economic impacts of these two major transformations. Different actors have different tools available and can interact in different ways, which define the governance modes that will be investigated in D8.2.

With this in mind, this report starts by reviewing and summarising selected findings of the GI-NI research based on analyses of the key drivers of digital transformation, globalisation, and migration and their impact on income inequality and skills in the EU. Section three connects such findings to the scenarios envisioned for potential futures and examines the challenges expected to arise under those scenarios. Section four identifies the risks and challenges associated with these scenarios, associated with both global development and local, socio-economic outcomes (i.e. skills demand and inequality). Section five first maps the key actors that are relevant to address the challenges identified above. It then discusses current and new policies that can address key challenges under the alternative scenarios, focusing on the role of different stakeholders. In doing so, it takes stock of the current status of the EU as a global actor and its ability to shape global developments in digital transformation and globalisation. It also identifies the national and subnational actors that can play a crucial role in selected policy options for tackling inequality and improving labour market outcomes. Section six concludes.

2. The impact of major transformations

2.1 Digital transformation¹

Technological change is a key driver of economic progress, which enables increased efficiency and value creation. However, the equitable distribution of productivity gains remains a challenge.

The world of business and work is being reshaped by the digital revolution, facing the labour market with many transformations and challenges. New technologies have heterogeneous impacts on the nature of work, exhibiting diverse effects that span across multiple dimensions. These effects not only differ among various groups of workers but also manifest discrepancies across firms and regions.

New technologies can enable firms to become more productive and grow faster, which can result in employment opportunities and, hence, stronger demand for labour. Firms adapt to and integrate technological advancements into their operations in distinct ways based on their characteristics and dynamics. In general, smaller firms are rather disadvantaged in terms of the infrastructure and resources to access and adopt cutting-edge technologies compared to larger firms. This discrepancy leads to a growing divide between small non-adopters and large adopters, where smaller firms face a higher risk of losing their market share and competitiveness (Rademakers and Zierahn-Weilage, 2023).

At the same time, the extent to which workers are able to respond to and are affected by the implementation of new technologies varies depending on factors such as their level of education and the capacity and willingness to engage in digital skills. Those with fewer qualifications and skills often face greater barriers in this process, and older individuals may be less inclined to engage with new technologies. Workers in specialised, routine-based tasks are particularly exposed to technological change and at risk of job displacement, unemployment and loss of income. These workers also face more obstacles in finding new jobs as the demand for their skills is expected to decline in view of new technological developments (Rademakers and Zierahn-Weilage, 2023).

Based on GI-NI research, ongoing technological transformation is not expected to lead to massive job losses. Historically, technological change has generated at least as many jobs as it destroys (Rademakers and Zierahn-Weilage, 2023). However, while the net employment effects of new technologies are expected to be limited in a broad perspective, they do lead to large shifts in the structure of jobs. This deteriorates mainly opportunities for certain groups of workers (e.g. those with a high share of routine tasks), amplifying existing

¹ This subsection builds on the analysis conducted in GI-NI WP3.

inequality and job polarisation. New technologies not only tend to exacerbate existing inequalities among workers, but they can also introduce new forms of inequality. GI-NI research shows that automation-exposed job seekers typically spend more time in unemployment because the occupations available to them rarely match their skill set, offering poor job-finding opportunities.

2.2 Globalisation²

Over the past decades, globalisation has been a transformative force, propelled by advancements in technology, liberalised trade policies, and increased cross-border investments, fostering growth and shaping economies. There is a broad consensus that globalisation and trade liberalisation have brought substantial welfare gains for many economies around the world by promoting consumers' and firms' options, inducing market competition and production specialisation. The distribution of these gains, however, has been uneven. In many advanced countries, medium-skilled and low-skilled workers have experienced negative labour market outcomes of increased imports from countries such as China. At the same time, those same countries have tended to specialise in high-skilled activities, such as R&D, management, and marketing, while medium- and low-skilled activities related to the fabrication of products (the 'factory work') have often been offshored to regions with low labour costs like Eastern Europe and China. This shift has raised inequality in terms of employment opportunities and wages (Los, 2023).

[GI-NI research](#) suggests that workers who are exposed to increased import competition are more likely to move to less affected regions or switch to other occupations or business functions than workers who are not. Two case studies, based on data from Germany and the Netherlands, show that the workers who adapted to increased import competition by changing their location or occupation experienced positive effects in terms of wages and job satisfaction. Nevertheless, not all workers can adapt effectively, and the adverse effects of this competition can be long-lasting. The available jobs often require capabilities and skills that the workers hit by intensified trade do not have and cannot acquire in the short run.

The job losses and inequality-increasing effects associated with the globalisation trend have led to a backlash against it, and recent data suggest a possible slowdown or even a shift in the globalisation trajectory. The COVID-19 pandemic, which underscored the vulnerabilities arising from high reliance on global supply chains, particularly in strategic sectors, has resulted in increasing debate about the need for policies that prioritise national interests over global cooperation. They advocate the protection of domestic industries and challenge

² This subsection builds on the analysis conducted in GI-NI WP4

the value of international agreements. These effects have been reinforced by rising geopolitical tension following Russia's aggression against Ukraine and heightened trade tensions between the US and China.

This evolving landscape has increased uncertainty in global trade and investment and impelled firms and businesses to consider repositioning their activities and production sites back to (or near to) the source country, so-called reshoring (or nearshoring). The terms 'slowbalisation' and 're-globalisation' have been increasingly used over the past few years. Recent evidence hints at reshoring and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows to the US in critical sectors, such as chips and EV batteries for electrical equipment. US government incentives through the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), Chips Act, and Infrastructure Bill aiming at protecting and promoting the local supply chains are the main drivers of these trends. The EU has adopted a much less confrontational approach than the US towards China; however, de-risking from China, mostly by reducing trade dependencies in strategic products and vulnerabilities of its supply chains, has become a priority.

Despite these global developments, concerns about the effects of globalisation on inequality remain warranted. First, it is still uncertain to what extent Western governments will continue to reduce trade linkages with China. Second, the reshoring of manufacturing activities is unlikely to lead to major mass employment. Production systems have evolved dramatically and larger use of technology will require less labour in manufacturing.

Finally, since the end of the global financial crisis, trade in business services and other services used as intermediate inputs by firms has been rising at a much faster pace than trade in goods. As opportunities to trade such services increase, enabled by the digital transformation, globalisation might well change in nature rather than in degree. Consequently, continued globalisation might affect, with both opportunities and challenges, other groups of workers with capabilities and skills other than those impacted until now.

2.3 Migration³

Migration can be driven by a variety of economic, social, political, and environmental factors. These factors can act as push and pull factors, influencing people to leave their country of origin and settle in a new location. The EU has experienced significant migration flows with an increase in the number of third-country nationals over the past decades, which accounts for 5.3% of the total population, of which slightly over half are women (according to Eurostat).

³ This subsection builds on the analysis conducted in GI-NI WP5

[GI-NI research](#) highlights that natives and migrants are not equally distributed across occupations, due to a lack of labour market knowledge and language proficiency of migrant workers. These disparities are further magnified when considering gender. Foreign-born workers, particularly women, encounter specific employment entry barriers that result in occupational segregation, deskilling, and over-qualification, thereby exacerbating inequality levels, as well as the gender gap in the labour market. Migrants often find employment in sectors stereotypical to gender norms, such as construction for men and caregiving and healthcare for women. This exacerbates the gender gap. Moreover, migrants are overrepresented in certain low and medium-skilled occupations, primarily in sectors like accommodation and food services. In this segmented labour market, migrants, especially women, struggle to access high-skill occupations and achieve upward mobility. Consequently, many migrants end up in jobs below their qualifications, resulting in overqualification.

Another notable finding of the [GI-NI research](#) is that contrary to expectations, income inequality within migrant countries in the EU discourages migration. Although factors such as migration networks, strong work ethics, education, and income cushion partially mitigate this effect (Aldaz et al., 2023), barriers to potential migration lead to missed economic development opportunities for both the origin and destination countries.

3. Future scenarios⁴

This section outlines the four distinct future scenarios, as described in the forthcoming GI-Ni research, driven by developments in the two major trends presented above, namely digital transformation and globalisation, until 2030. These two transformations are believed to be the key drivers of changes concerning labour market outcomes and inequality under that horizon. Alternative futures involve hypothetical scenarios that consider progress versus stagnation of the digital transformation and further globalisation versus deglobalisation⁵. In addition, the economic and labour market outcomes associated with each scenario are discussed, focusing on inequality and skill demand. The discussion provides insights into potential solutions and tools that are used in the last section to identify relevant actors and policy options.

As illustrated in GI-NI D7.3, building on the two main transformations four possible scenarios are identified (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The four scenarios as driven by digital transformation (vertical axis) and globalisation (horizontal axis).

Source : GI-NI D7.3, p. 13

⁴ This section summarises the main point of the foresight work done in GI-NI WP7

⁵ It is assumed that (legal) migration is largely driven by globalisation and other developments within the scenarios, such as geopolitical tensions and wars. For that reason, we consider potential developments in migration within each scenario but not a separate driver.

Each scenario foresees a different speed in the development of digital transformation and globalisation, as well as in the interplay between two forces. While the consensus is that digital transformation (vertical axis) will not stop, the scenarios reckon an uncertainty around the speed of the adoption of new technologies, and the possibility of slow embracing of technological progress is considered. Similarly, while globalisation (horizontal axis) will not stop by 2030, relocation of production and rising protectionism due to escalating geopolitical and trade tensions can result in fragmentation in global trade, prompting a movement towards “slowbalisation” or even deglobalisation. These two transformations and the pace of their development do not proceed in isolation; they are interlinked and can reinforce or interfere with each other. We briefly recall here the main features of the four scenarios.

Scenario 1 (Empowered by Technology): This scenario envisages a world where digital transformation accelerates and industries rapidly adopt technological changes. However, this progress is coupled with a decline in globalisation or deglobalisation, where economic and geopolitical factors give rise to polarisation and forming economic power blocks, primarily led by the US and China. As a result, the potential gains and losses associated with the technological progress are expected to stay primarily within each block, which in turn limits the level of knowledge and technology transfer/sharing between blocks. This will also affect labour mobility where work-related migration between power blocks decreases, although migration within power blocks increases. Overall, in this scenario, the impact of technological advances is expected to be partially offset by deglobalisation.

Scenario 2 (Techtopia): This scenario foresees an acceleration in both digital transformation and globalisation. Technological advancements, particularly in AI and robotics, together with more dynamic global cooperation, catalyse innovation and heighten efficiency and productivity. These developments foster economic growth and welfare, create more job opportunities and increase wages. Global collaboration becomes even more dynamic, fostering international trade. Accordingly, migration and labour mobility to and within the EU will increase. The two trends reinforce each other.

Scenario 3 (Economic Minimalism): This scenario paints a picture of a world where diminished cooperation and falling knowledge exchange between power blocks lead to a stagnation of digital transformation. The slowdown in technological advancements results in stagnation in labour productivity. Global trade in goods and services also declines, contributing to a slowdown in economic growth. Escalating tensions between nations, driven by prioritisation of national interest, lead to further polarisation and decreased migration between blocks.

Scenario 4 (Analog Alliance): In this scenario, the initial enthusiasm for rapid technological adoption diminishes, resulting in a stagnation in digital transformation. Despite this, globalisation continues to thrive. The slowdown in technological investments, however, falls short of yielding the expected boost in productivity and economic growth. Nevertheless, the increase in global trade and openness is expected to enhance migration.

4. Risks and Challenges

The anticipated future scenarios, while bearing some positive outcomes, are also poised to introduce a range of risks and economic and social challenges, underscoring the necessity for policy interventions. These risks and challenges are likely to materialise at two distinct levels. On a macro scale, overarching challenges will arise from the nature and pace of technological transformation and globalisation. Stakeholders, including policymakers and private entities such as large corporations and multinationals, wield the capacity to influence, if not mould, these unfolding transformations. At a more local level, risks and challenges will materialise as consequences of these pivotal shifts, in the form of suboptimal labour market outcomes (like unemployment) and widening inequalities. The following subsections explain and exemplify such challenges within the framework of the four scenarios.

4.1 Transformations at the global level: key challenges

Under scenario 1 (Empowered by Technology), a key macro challenge will be managing technological gaps. With deglobalisation trends limiting knowledge and technology transfer between economic power blocks, disparities in technological advancements can potentially lead to unequal access to innovative solutions and economic opportunities and countries or blocks lagging behind, hence the emergence of technological gaps between blocks. This is likely a more significant risk for those blocks already struggling to keep pace with the technological leaders.

Under Scenario 2 (Techtopia), which is the most promising in terms of developments of the trends, one key challenge will be to ensure Inclusive growth. Policymakers will need to focus on policies that ensure the benefits of technological advancements and openness are equitably distributed across society.

Under scenario 3 (Economic Minimalism), a major challenge will be to address technological stagnation and potential economic recession. In an environment of diminished openness and knowledge exchange, policies that stimulate innovation, research and development, and digital transformation are crucial to prevent stagnation and boost labour productivity and growth.

In Scenario 4 (Analog Alliance), a key challenge lies in fostering technological advancement. In an environment where technological adoption stagnates, businesses with lower productivity are at risk of declining competitiveness within a globally integrated world. This

could potentially lead to a market exit for some companies, consequently exacerbating unemployment.

4.2 Socio-economic outcomes at the local level: key challenges

Automation and digital innovations are changing quite dramatically the demand for skills. The growing need for professionals with expertise in AI, machine learning, and data science, as well as skills in programming languages (such as Python and R) and skills related to big data processing, among others, is likely to continue. At the same time, hybrid skill sets and non-technical (e.g. teamwork) and human (e.g. critical thinking creativity) skills are gaining importance. So in the scenarios where technological transformation is predicted to progress rapidly (scenarios 1 and 2), there will be a significant increase in the demand for these skills. This may not be the case in the alternative scenarios. Skills demand is likely to vary significantly across the four scenarios based on the level of technological advancement, globalisation, and economic growth projected in each scenario. In general, the acceleration of technological transformation is likely to disproportionately affect workers, with those particularly lacking these skills and/or with lower educational attainments staying behind. In contrast, workers with a technical and interpersonal background and workers who better adapt to the new technologies are likely to benefit the most from these developments.

As mentioned above, inequality is likely to manifest as an issue across all four scenarios, albeit to varying degrees and in different forms. Both digital transformation and globalisation can penalise groups of workers and firms that cannot align with the new developments and, therefore, stay behind. In the context of scenarios where both developments take the same progressive direction and bolster each other, the adverse effects of inequality are likely to intensify, exposing vulnerable firms and workers to more competition despite stouter overall improvement in economic growth and employment.

Under Scenario 1 (Empowered by Technology) socioeconomic inequality may arise within economic power blocks due to unequal access to technological advancements and economic gains. The polarisation and deglobalisation trends could exacerbate income disparities between different regions or groups within each block. The rapid digital transformation but limited knowledge and technology transfer between power blocks may lead to heightened demand for specialised technical skills within each economic block. Industries heavily reliant on advanced technologies may require expertise in areas like AI, data analytics, cybersecurity, and digital innovation.

‘Techoptia’, which is the most promising scenario in terms of economic growth, job creation, and wage growth, appears to be the most unequal one. Technological advancements and globalisation may disproportionately benefit certain sectors or skilled

workers, leading to wage discrepancies and income disparities. With accelerated digital transformation and enhanced global cooperation driving innovation and economic growth, the demand for a broad range of skills is expected to increase. Apart from technical skills, there may be a need for transversal skills like adaptability, creativity, critical thinking, and cross-cultural communication to support collaboration and global trade. Globalisation is expected to increase the demand for more specialised tasks while, at the same time, reducing the employment opportunities for low- and medium-skilled workers, often including mostly women, by exposing them to more competition effects from outside. Based on recent years' experience, a further push for globalisation is likely to put higher pressures on small firms as more openness creates higher competition effects by large international firms that have the resources and capacity to adopt technologies at a faster pace.

By contrast, the 'Economic Minimalism' scenario, with stagnation in both digitalisation and globalisation, might create a less severe impact on income disparities in the short term; however, diminished productivity growth will limit job opportunities, wage increases, and overall economic prosperity. Reduced global trade and cooperation may further exacerbate disparities within and between countries but at the cost of economic slowdown and overall income loss. Economic stagnation and diminished productivity growth can contribute to socioeconomic inequality by limiting job opportunities, wage increases, and overall economic prosperity. Vulnerable groups, including low-skilled workers, migrants, and women, are particularly at risk. Reduced global trade and cooperation may further exacerbate disparities within and between countries. In this scenario, skills demand may be less focused on cutting-edge technology and more on traditional skills that support basic economic activities. General employability skills, vocational training, and adaptability may become more relevant in the context of slower technological advancement and economic growth. Finally, as migration may experience a slowdown as a result of reduced job opportunities, economic uncertainties, and restrictions on movement between countries, labour markets may experience increasing shortages.

Lastly, under scenario 4 (Analog Alliance), where global trade and openness thrive, socioeconomic inequality can persist if technological progress lags behind expectations. Income differentials may arise based on access to and adoption of digital technologies, potentially widening the gap between tech-savvy and less technologically adept populations. As technological progress stagnates, the demand for skills may vary across different industries. Sectors experiencing subdued technological adoption might prioritise skills like project management, organisational development, and cross-border communications, while industries driving global trade could seek skills related to supply chain management, digital marketing, and international relations. As global trade continues to thrive, migration patterns could contribute to improving labour market outcomes

While technology adoption has the potential to raise welfare and growth and induce an efficient allocation of workers to productive fast-growing firms, it implies larger job displacement and restructuring costs for workers and firms. Especially small ones are likely to be exposed to heightened competition. The technological transformation can exacerbate disparities between major corporations and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which often struggle to adopt technology. This may result in larger companies becoming more appealing to skilled technical professionals. As a result, SMEs may encounter growing challenges in attracting and retaining technical talent, putting their competitive advantages at risk as they struggle to compete with the staffing competence of larger firms

Overall, while income inequality may manifest differently across the four scenarios, the underlying dynamics of access to resources, opportunities, and benefits of economic and technological advancements can contribute to disparities in income distribution. Policymakers need to be vigilant across all scenarios to address these inherent inequalities and work towards fostering more equitable and inclusive societies.

One key message is that even in the best-case scenario, inequality may increase despite the advantages that the prosperous innovative economy will bring in terms of job and income opportunities. On the upside, economic gains create room for redistribution policy and, hence, the capacity to combat inequality. More resources will be available to design and implement strategies for more equitable distribution.

In the other scenarios, despite potentially less unfavourable outcomes for inequality, the potential negative impacts, either through loss in competitiveness, lower innovation, growth, and productivity, also create more challenges and constraints for policymakers in designing a more inclusive and sustainable growth model. In the face of overstretched resources, the room for policy interventions is limited, and the need for prioritisation becomes inevitable.

In addition, in all scenarios, there will be a shift in the labour market landscape through changing the nature of work driven by technology, which will lead to an increase in demand for certain skills, with some scenarios experiencing very rapid and significant changes. Across all four scenarios, adaptable and diverse skill sets are likely to be valuable as individuals navigate shifting job markets, technological landscapes, and global economic trends.

Lastly, rapid technological growth is also expected to further exacerbate gender inequalities in wages and labour force participation. Despite the improvements, women's participation within STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Maths) sectors remains low in the EU,

and the tech sector is still predominantly male-dominated. Accordingly, labour market shifts in skill needs are likely to further disadvantage women's economic positions.

The following sections focus on identifying key actors and delineating their potential roles in implementing policies and strategies to tackle the identified challenges.

5. Actors and policies to address the challenges

5.1 Mapping the actors

Drawing on the idea that challenges associated with technological transformation and globalisation can arise at two distinct levels, global and local, EU policy interventions can be envisioned across two primary tiers, external (at the global level) and local (within the EU), prompting engagement from diverse stakeholders.

At the global level, the EU, as a prominent global actor, possesses the capacity to collaborate with international counterparts, including private entities, to potentially influence or shape the trajectory of technological transformation and globalisation.

Within the EU, the EU, national, and sub-national levels, interactions among various actors can be instrumental in responding to significant transformations and mitigating adverse socioeconomic outcomes as identified under the outlined scenarios, notably in the realms of skill demand and inequality.

Against this background, we start by mapping the key actors (see Figure 2) that we believe are relevant to address the challenges, and the tools they have available. In the ensuing discussion, we first examine the role that the EU plays in the global context in relation to the two main transformations. We then delineate the roles that other actors could play in addressing challenges at the local level, with a focus on selected policy domains.

Figure 2. Mapping actors, tools, and challenges

Source: Authors' elaboration

Figure 2 maps a list of relevant actors, grouping them according to their governmental and non-governmental nature. They are different in nature and have different tools available, which can be used in different governance settings. While this will be covered in D8.2, this report focuses on the EU and whether and how it can influence the trajectory of technological transformation and globalisation, and whether and how it can contribute to societal progress by improving labour market outcomes and inequality. In doing so, the EU interacts with the other identified actors. At the global level, the EU is faced with other international powers, international organisations, and multilateral and bilateral institutional and governance settings that affect its modus operandi by constraining or enhancing its role as a global actor. Within the EU, the EU as a supranational institution defines the

regulatory framework of the single market and holds normative powers that together define common values and objectives, like those of a more competitive, fairer and more inclusive Europe. In this context, the EU interacts with national governments and sub-national authorities (e.g. regions), as well as companies and other stakeholders (e.g. social partners).

The next sections dive into these two dimensions, highlighting policy instruments that can be used to achieve EU policy objectives and address upcoming challenges.

5.2 The global challenges: the EU as a global actor

In a global context, increasingly shaped by power politics and technological leadership that can determine both economic strength and geopolitical power, the role of the EU as a global actor is crucial in determining its ability to address broad challenges. This involves examining the extent of the EU's influence on global technology governance and globalisation.

This question is not new. The [TRIGGER project](#) formulated a model to investigate the concept of EU actorness (see Figure 3), which they made dependent on a variety of factors, internal and external, as identified in the literature. Their main point is that the degree of actorness ultimately determines how effectively the EU can pursue its goals. Hence, actorness is a precondition for effectiveness in global governance.

Figure 3. TRIGGER project model of EU actorness

Source: [Renda \(2020\)](#)

Among the many findings of the projects, two are of specific interest to this report, and they relate to the EU's technological influence. First, according to the TRIGGER analysis, the EU has been found to have a low level of legal authority, hence strong influence in affecting patterns, on key technologies like AI, blockchain, open-source software and standards. The main reason is that the EU Treaties do not confer competencies to the EU level in these areas, where decisions are made at the national level and most often left to the market. This

indicates limited capacity for direct enforcement of change. Second, the EU enjoys significant influence or soft power, as it incorporates values and cultural aspects, which make it a role model for others that surpasses its formal legal authority. This makes it an important global governance actor in the eyes of other nations. However, EU credibility in the technology domain has been suffering from shortcomings in consistency across digital policies. For instance, vague European values and ambitions for creating tech giants comparable to those in the US have resulted in mixed outcomes. The EU's technological naiveté and failure to anticipate changes in the internet landscape, such as the dominance of proprietary platforms, are examples of such shortcomings.

Some recent signs have indicated a change of direction, driven by some initiatives under the von der Leyen Commission concerning data strategies. Interestingly, the initial commitment to global technological openness and boosting its share of the global data economy has been reviewed in light of successive geopolitical developments, such as the Russian invasion of Ukraine and heightened US-China trade tensions. In addition, disruptive and rapid advances in AI, like ChatGPT, have prompted the EU to question its approach and reassess its strategies.

These geopolitical events have led the EU to acknowledge two major changes in the global context. First, the fundamental threats to the global multilateral rule-based system made by the US-China power race and Russia's aggression against Ukraine represent a major change in the conditions in which the EU operates and has been able to prosper. This change implies that economic efficiency is no longer the key criterion for resource allocation, and economic security has become a more important driver.⁶ Second, technology has been recognised as a key source of economic but also geopolitical power. Technological leadership matters.

In response to it, strategic autonomy and economic security have taken centre stage in the EU debate. The concepts, which emphasise the EU's ability and readiness to shape international relations and act independently if necessary, have implications for both the EU's position on the global stage in terms of technology and trade. Such a shift has led to a number of initiatives, some of which were set up in response to US policies, notably the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) (see Box 1 for an overview of the main initiatives). Although strategic autonomy offers a clear direction for the EU, it does not resolve all integration gaps between various policies. The rise of strategic autonomy necessitates a renewed reflection on the EU as a recognised actor, both at the global level and internally.

⁶ See for instance Alcidi et al. (2023)

Box 1. EU initiatives for open strategic autonomy and economic security

As a response to the IRA, to the impact of the energy crisis and the Russian war against Ukraine, in February 2023, the Commission published the Green Deal Industrial Plan, a strategy for 'enhancing the competitiveness of Europe's net-zero industry'. It includes a new regulatory framework on net-zero technologies (Net Zero Industry Act, NZIA) and critical raw materials (Critical Raw Materials Act, CRMA), as well as a revision of existing state aid rules.

The Net-Zero Industry Act (NZIA)

NZIA can be seen as most directly responding to the US IRA, even though the current legislative proposal looks very different from anything pursued by the IRA and builds on EU strengths and (legal) capacity to regulate the internal market. Some parts of the NZIA, such as provisions on permitting, access to funding, and regulatory sandboxes, can be seen as trying to address red tape in the economy and simplifying processes. It also includes a proposal to have minimum domestic production targets for strategic net-zero technologies, though there is not yet agreement on the list of strategic net-zero technologies. Lastly, the funding is still unclear. The EP supports using at least 25% of ETS auction revenues to support the objectives of the NZIA. This would not necessarily lead to additional cleantech financing in Europe, as EU Member States, by and large, already spend most of their ETS revenues on objectives considered in line with EU climate goals.

Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA)

The CRMA aims at securing the supply of CRMs to support the manufacturing of net-zero (and digital) technologies. Along with a proposal setting conditions and benchmarks for the development of domestic mining and recycling capacity in the EU, the Act comes with an EU CRM strategy on trade diversification, international cooperation, coordination of finance, skills and R&D and identifies a subgroup of 'strategic raw materials' that are highly important for strategic (green) applications. Crucially, the Act does not mobilise new resources but provides for a European Critical Raw Materials Board (Member States representatives and Commission) to coordinate existing financing mechanisms.

Revised state aid rules: Temporary Crisis and Transition Framework

Building upon the Temporary Crisis Framework adopted in the wake of Russia's war against Ukraine, the new Temporary Crisis and Transition framework prolongs the possibility for Member States to support the deployment of renewable energy technologies and industrial decarbonisation while expanding the scope of eligible schemes to those supporting clean tech manufacturing as well as critical raw materials projects. The framework allows for more flexibility in allocating national budgets and a more generous form of state aid if a Member State can credibly demonstrate that additional aid is necessary to avoid investments from being diverted away from the EU (so-called matching aid). The latter can be seen as an explicit response to the extensive subsidies offered through the IRA.

The Economic Security packages

In addition to the initiative above, the EU has outlined a number of new measures aimed at boosting its economic security. The focus was first (in 2023) on offering a comprehensive approach to managing risks related to economic linkages, which are evolving quickly in the current geopolitical and technological environment and increasingly merging with security concerns. This is why the EU

must develop a comprehensive approach to commonly identifying, assessing and managing risks to its economic security. The Strategy focuses on the assessment of risks to economic security in four areas: i) risks to the resilience of supply chains, including energy security; ii) risks to physical and cyber security of critical infrastructure; iii) risks related to technology security and technology leakage; iv) risks of weaponisation of economic dependencies or economic coercion.

These initiatives have been complemented by another package in 2024 focussing on trade and research to enhance its economic security and manage emerging risks. They include: i) **screening of foreign investments** into the EU to prevent investments that may pose a risk to the EU's security; ii) having a more coordinated approach to the **EU's exports of dual-use goods** to ensure they do not fall into the wrong hands (e.g. advanced technologies can be used to enhance the military capacities of actors who may use these against the EU); iii) **research**: the Commission is looking into ways to support research and development in technologies which can be used for different purposes, and at how to enhance research security across the EU.

In this less benevolent context, the limited EU's influence in global technology and governance may not be up to the challenge of pursuing strategic autonomy. Such a challenge is likely to become more pronounced under adverse scenarios in which geopolitical fragmentation leads to international policies shaped by superpowers and economic fragmentation. Changing the situation will require the EU to be bolder in several policy areas, from industrial policy to trade policy.

5.3 The EU internal challenges: actors and policies

This section focuses on three policy areas: employment, enterprises, and gender. It identifies relevant actors, their current roles, and what they could do to address the challenges posed by technological transformation and globalisation and their potential negative impacts. As will be illustrated, in each of these policy areas, the EU has been an active actor in setting normative objectives, providing funds, and defining regulatory frameworks within the single market to enhance employment, promote competitiveness, and combat gender inequality.

It should be noted, however, that the EU has limited competencies (legal authority, according to the TRIGGER model) in social policies (employment and gender), where member states hold the power to legislate. To overcome such limitations, the EU has increasingly resorted to tools available under the single market framework and advocated for a fairer and more inclusive Europe and encouraged national governments, as well as a variety of other stakeholders, particularly social partners, to work in that direction.

5.3.1 Policy options for employment

Reskilling and upskilling strategies

In the context of employment policies, since the late 1990s increasing attention has been devoted to policies aimed at investing in people to make them resilient to major transformations. Such novelty was driven by the emergence of new academic research in social science which introduced the concept of **social investment** (somewhat in opposition to social security) as a necessary tool to deal with societal transformation led by the post-industrial world and the larger participation of women in the labour market. This new concept, which emphasises equipping citizens with tools to prepare for future risks rather than intervening ex-post with monetary support, gained political momentum at the EU level with the adoption of the Lisbon Agenda in 2000.⁷ This marked a paradigm shift in the role of the EU concerning employment and social policies.

One of the key changes brought about by this paradigm shift was increased attention to policies such as early childcare, education and care, parental leave, and adult learning. The latter, in particular, represents a significant innovation, embodying the idea that further investments in vocational and educational training (VET) programmes and, more broadly, in adult learning—including lifelong learning—can support and enhance individuals' professional competitiveness and employability. By fostering their ability to adapt to new developments, continuously learn new skills, and diversify their skill sets, these investments aim to make the workforce more resilient and adaptable

In practice, training programmes can support job seekers with job development and placement. These programmes are typically short-cycled and led by local public organisations, like the Public Employment Services (PES). They help applicants with soft skills (or work-readiness) training as well as occupational skills training. Life-long learning, in comparison, engages workers in educational activities that are not exclusively related to the job they have. If, instead, firms and workers are encouraged to invest in skills they do not currently possess but might be relevant in other occupations or roles, these workers would become more resilient to changes in the intensity of competition. This approach would also make them more adaptable.

⁷ See Alcidi and Corti (2022) offer a reconstruction of the evolution of the EU social agenda from the late 1990s, and show as the EU advocacy for social investment as a new social policy paradigm has been increasing over the years

Relevant actors

In recent years most EU countries have tried to favour actions to support workers. Yet it is the European Commission that has led the way in this area⁸.

The EU since the Lisbon Agenda (2000), over the last two decades, many binding and non-binding initiatives⁹ on lifelong/adult learning have been launched at the EU level. Among them, the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#) (EPSR, 2017)¹⁰, which defines the EU principles and priorities in the area of employment and social policies, is the most relevant. The EPSR contains as a first principle “Education, training and life-long learning” and states “Everyone has the right to quality and inclusive education, training and life-long learning in order to maintain and acquire skills that enable them to participate fully in society and manage successfully transitions in the labour market”. This is the recognition that major transformations, like technological progress and globalization (as well as the green transition) can pose challenges to workers and that education and adult learning can support to cope with these challenges. In this context, the EPSR contains several actions aiming at translating the principle into measures. The most recent initiatives include the New Skills Agenda for Europe¹¹. This strategy aims to support Member States in addressing the skills gap and increasing the level of preparedness of the workforce. It focuses on equipping national governments with the necessary measures to prioritise basic and digital skills for all. One of the key actions under this strategy is the Recommendation on Upskilling Pathways, which supports low-skilled individuals in progressing towards an upper secondary qualification or equivalent. In an effort to improve existing skills and training in new ones, the European Commission has introduced the Pact for Skills¹², which aims to mobilise and incentivise stakeholders (including industry, employers, social partners, etc.) to make concrete commitments to upskill and reskill efforts. Overall, the European Commission¹³ is playing a pivotal role in:

⁸ See <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=1146>

⁹ For instance the ‘Education & Training 2020 Strategic Framework – ET2020’ (Council of the European Union, 2009), whose aim was to make the EU “the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world” (p. 1). The ‘Council Recommendation on upskilling pathways: new opportunities for adults’ (Council of the European Union, 2016) that targeted the low-skilled, regardless their working conditions.

¹⁰ In March 2021, a EPSR action plan was presented, determining a new EU headline objective of 60 % of individuals (aged 16-64) engaging in training every year by 2030 (European Commission, 2021a). This target was confirmed by the Porto declaration in 2021, demonstrating again the greatest degree of political commitment to adult learning.

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223&langId=en>

¹² https://pact-for-skills.ec.europa.eu/index_en

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1530&langId=en>

- Policy Development: Initiating and proposing new legislation tailored to the evolving needs of the European labour market, particularly legislation that enhances vocational education and training systems across member states.
- Law Enforcement: Ensuring that EU laws and regulations are uniformly applied and adhered to across all member states, thus maintaining a standardised approach to skills development.
- Funding and Grants: Through the European Social Fund (ESF), which is part of the EU common budget, the EU provides financial support to improve employment opportunities across the EU, raise living standards, and assist people in getting better skills and improving their job prospects.
- Program Implementation: Overseeing the implementation of EU-wide initiatives, which aims to ensure that more people acquire the high-level skills needed to compete in a globalised economy.
- Partnerships and Collaboration: Facilitating partnerships between governments, educational institutions, and industry leaders to modernise education and training systems in response to industrial and technological changes.

In this area, the EU does not work in a vacuum and other actors, national and international, have recognised the challenges faced by workers and taken action.

Public Employment Services: At the national level, the EU relies on Public Employment Services to develop effective and inclusive investment strategies for training and upskilling workers. The reach and capacity of national Public Employment Services vary depending on the country, its structure, and authority at the national level. However, they are not the only actors involved in addressing this challenge. Other stakeholders, such as workers, companies, public authorities, education institutions, training providers, and social partners, also contribute to improving the quality of services provided by Public Employment Services.

On a global scale, several international organisations promote reskilling and upskilling, mostly through initiatives that facilitate knowledge sharing between countries, issuing guidelines, monitoring trends, and providing financial and technical assistance to develop national reskilling ecosystems. Among them, the United Nations and its agencies, such as the International Labour Organization (ILO), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), support member countries in developing national policies focused on lifelong learning and skills development. The World Bank provides financial and technical assistance to developing countries for investing in education, training, and skills development programs. Their key contribution is advice and technical assistance to help governments develop education policies suitable for their countries' circumstances. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) monitors trends in skills demand and

supply and issues guidelines and recommendations to member countries on developing effective reskilling strategies.

Occupational Mobility and job-matching

Occupational mobility or switching between occupations or business functions is often hampered by a lack of skills. Workers in one occupation do not possess the required capabilities to be productive in a different one. Well-designed upskilling and reskilling programs facilitate the mobility of workers across sectors and occupations, helping them absorb the displacement shock due to the competition effects raised by digital transformation and globalisation. Considering the expected change in the dynamics of the labour market in the face of technological advancement, policies should focus on increasing occupational mobility into sectors with growing demand. This will contribute to boosting productivity but also generate viable pathways for vulnerable workers to secure employment.

In addition, policies are also needed to address the barriers to labour mobility across regions. Policies regarding social security, pensions, and housing can facilitate the movement of workers across borders. Housing-related constraints (sale, purchase, taxes) often play an important role in adaptation when moving to a new location. Also, in several European countries, workers who adapt by switching from one occupation to another face problems regarding institutional savings for the period after retiring. If job switches no longer affect the expectations regarding post-retirement income negatively, workers will be less discouraged from adapting by finding jobs in different occupations. So, the costs of adapting can be lowered by streamlining pension regulations.

In facilitating adaptation through relocating to other regions or switching to a different occupation or business function, the national and EU-wide policies could complement each other in providing and improving the opportunities for workers to be flexible. These policies at large call for cooperation and coordination between the EU Member States, and across national, regional, and local governments.

Furthermore, one of the main challenges that hinder labour mobility is the skills-occupation mismatch. This is also recognised to be one of the factors behind skill shortages faced by European firms. It is assumed that skill-occupation mismatches exacerbate in view of rapid technological transformation and the subsequent increase in demand for digital and technical skills.

Initiatives such as 'matchmaking' between job-seekers and employers put forward in the EU aim to improve mobility by better linking job-seekers and suitable employment opportunities across sectors and regions.

The technology-induced displacement and inequality call for bigger and stronger involvement of welfare state institutions to support the relocation and transition of affected workers for a smooth adjustment. Directing job seekers more actively towards jobs with better prospects can be done, for instance, through establishing efficient communication and information transfer about available alternative options and possibilities in growing occupations.

While these policies attempt to address the adverse distributional impact of the transformative forces, these forces particularly digitalisation and automation can be employed to create and develop innovative tools and a more targeted 'Recommender System' for improving job and skill mismatches and therefore improve job mobility.

Relevant actors

The EU is currently actively working to increase fair labour mobility within Europe by addressing the barriers and ensuring the protection of mobile workers. Key initiatives such as Fair European Labour Mobility¹⁴ and Social Security Coordination¹⁵ are steps in this direction.¹⁶ The main actors involved in these initiatives are:

European Commission: The European Commission is responsible for proposing legislation and policies related to fair labour mobility within the EU. It works closely with the European Labour Authority (ELA) and other stakeholders to develop and implement initiatives that promote fair mobility and protect the rights of mobile workers.

Member States: Each EU member state plays a crucial role in implementing and enforcing EU rules on labour mobility. They are responsible for ensuring that the rights and working conditions of mobile workers are protected within their territories. Member states also collaborate with the ELA and other EU institutions to coordinate enforcement efforts and share information.

¹⁴ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/labour-mobility/>

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=849>

¹⁶ See also <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/eu-labour-mobility/> and <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/labour-mobility-eu-recent-trends-and-policies>

Social Partners: Social partners, including trade unions and employer organisations, are actively involved in promoting fair labour mobility within Europe. They participate in consultations, negotiations, and discussions on labour mobility policies and initiatives. Social partners also play a role in safeguarding the rights and interests of workers and employers in the context of labour mobility.

Overall, the shift in labour demand can lead to changes in employment opportunities and job requirements. The lag in equipping workers with skills that complement new technologies is a challenge in the labour market that hinders the broader diffusion of innovation within economies. Addressing this skills gap is crucial to ensure that workers can adapt to the changing demands of the labour market. Also, cultivating Job mobility and job-matching can increase resilience to the changes and, at the same time, enhance productivity. Along with these changes, advances in productivity can create high-quality employment that contributes to growth.

5.3.2 Policy options to support small firms and businesses

To cope with the adverse consequences of technological change, policies and schemes should not only target the workers but also support employers, particularly the smaller firms, to keep up with technological advancements. Enabling employers to incorporate new technologies competitively is critical for adapting to the future of work. Firms not only need the right infrastructure (such as broadband internet access) but also the right set of skills and complementary organisational change to successfully adopt new technologies (Rademakers and Zierahn-Weilage, 2023). Additional initiatives of this nature must be developed and implemented to ensure that companies maintain their competitiveness on a global scale.

Relevant actors

EU and national governments: The EU offers various programs to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) access advisory and financial support for innovation and to enhance their competitiveness.¹⁷ European Industrial and Digital Strategy also focuses on SMEs to enable them to remain resilient and competitive at the global level.¹⁸ National governments, including government agencies and regulatory bodies, also play a role by providing direct financial support in the form of grants or subsidies and other financial

¹⁷ https://eisma.ec.europa.eu/programmes_en

¹⁸ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/strategy_en. See also https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/chapter/enterprise.html?root_default=SUM_1_CODED%3D19&locale=en

inducements, such as tax incentives to encourage firms and small businesses to invest in digital technologies.

Industry associations and trade organisations: Industry associations and trade organisations can provide resources, networking opportunities, and industry-specific knowledge to support firms in their digital transformation. These organisations often organise conferences, workshops, and training programs to educate firms about the latest digital trends and technologies.

Technology companies and solution providers: Technology companies and solution providers can offer a wide range of digital tools, platforms, and services that enable firms to adopt and implement digital technologies effectively. These companies provide solutions for cloud computing, data analytics, artificial intelligence, Internet of Things (IoT) etc. Also, consulting firms and digital transformation specialists provide expertise and guidance to firms undergoing digital transformation. They help firms, particularly SMEs, to assess their current capabilities, develop digital strategies, identify technology solutions, and manage the implementation process.

5.3.3 Policy options to promote gender equality

Despite increased connectivity and digital work opportunities, a gender digital divide continues to persist, affecting women's access to technology and the internet. The stereotypes and gender norms continue to hold back women in the digital sector. To achieve gender equality in the face of technological transformation, women need equal access to technology and digital training.

Additionally, as GI-NI research shows, a significant part of the gender wage gap is driven by the gender difference in firm-specific wage premia, as women are mostly working at firms with a lower wage premium. In addition, women work less often in larger firms, which are more likely to innovate, engage in international trade, and pay flexible wages. The analysis also shows that the incentive wage schemes offered by these firms are mostly based on overtime hours, which are less accessible to women. Accordingly, there is a risk that innovation negatively affects gender equality as new technologies that support performance-based pay could widen gender wage gaps (Rademakers and Zierahn-Weilage, 2023). Therefore, policies should promote and support flexible work arrangements and facilitate, for example, parental leave, access to affordable and high-quality childcare, etc., to ensure that the larger firms, which are supposedly the main adopters of technological advances, remain accessible to women. Gender-based wage discrimination, however, remains a widespread issue. Efforts to address this include promoting diversity and equity

in staffing, union, and leadership positions for women, as well as promoting equitable pay, benefits, and access to social protections.

Gender bias and stereotypes in STEM fields disadvantage women by limiting their access to resources, opportunities, and mentorship, thereby hindering their professional growth. The underrepresentation of women in digital innovations perpetuates gender bias by reinforcing male-dominated perspectives in technological development, resulting in products and solutions that often fail to address the needs and experiences of women. Therefore, when considering solutions, it is crucial to incorporate social innovations that foster institutional culture change, aimed at reducing gender bias and discrimination in career choices and opportunities.

Relevant actors

The EU, along with specialised institutions such as the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), has been working collaboratively to find long-lasting solutions to the gender digital divide. Various actions are being implemented in the EU to strengthen digital skills, digital entrepreneurship, and the participation of women in statistics, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Lifelong learning programs, mentorships, and traineeships for young women in ICT and STEM have been proposed as strategies to overcome this digital divide.¹⁹

The Grand Coalition for Digital Jobs and Growth, led by the European Commission, is a multi-stakeholder partnership that aims to address the shortfall in the number of European citizens with ICT professional skills and to exploit the employment creation potential of ICT, including the participation of the European Centre for Women and Technology²⁰.

In addition, in recent years, several policies and initiatives have been trying to address the gender pay gap. For instance, the Gender Pay Transparency Directive²¹, aims to ensure transparency in pay by requiring companies to disclose information on their gender pay gap. The pay system should be also based on gender-neutral criteria.

At the national level, governments can play a role through policies that advocate gender equality in labour market. National governments are also key in allocating resources to

¹⁹ See for example <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/policy-areas/digital-agenda>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/women-digital>

²¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20230327IPR78545/gender-pay-gap-parliament-adopts-new-rules-on-binding-pay-transparency-measures>

support initiatives aimed at reducing gender disparities in education and employment. They can also implement programs that provide vocational education and skills training for women.

Industry associations and trade unions can also advocate for policies and practices that promote gender equality within the workplace, such as equal pay, equal opportunities for career advancement, and work-life balance initiatives. These organizations can also provide resources and support to their members in implementing measures that equip women with equal income opportunities.

Finally, to challenge gender stereotypes that affect women's occupational roles, educational institutions can take part by providing women with knowledge, skills, and values that help them in their choice of and advancements in their careers.

6. Concluding remarks

Irrespective of the specific scenario that unfolds, as defined in D7.3, the EU will face substantial challenges. Recent events, including the conflict in Ukraine and escalating tensions between China and the US, have created an unfavourable global landscape for the EU. The mounting pressure to compete for technological supremacy, primarily driven by the US and China, presents a considerable hurdle. Moreover, the historical EU prosperity rooted in openness and free trade faces threats, posing a significant risk to the EU's economic model. Against the backdrop of these evolving trends and a potential worsening of circumstances, the EU is reassessing its stance, with the concepts of strategic autonomy and economic security taking centre stage in EU deliberations. These shifts are redefining the EU's role as a global actor and could lead to a renewed approach to international cooperation and policy actions. A new industrial strategy for the EU and renewed focus on trade agreements are likely to prove key to move in this direction.

Furthermore, ongoing labour market transitions catalysed by technological advancements are anticipated to result in worker displacement, job realignment, and, in the short term, job losses in certain sectors. Conversely, some industries may encounter challenges in securing workers with the requisite skills. Even under the most favourable scenario, significant labour market challenges are anticipated, necessitating policy intervention to mitigate such impacts. Similarly, inequality is unlikely to reduce as a market outcome. This implies a critical need for policies to mitigate inequality. The capacity, both in terms of resources and political capital, to implement such policies will depend on the availability of resources.

The report identifies multiple global, national and sub-national actors, including both public and private entities, that can play a role in addressing these challenges with their respective tools and capabilities. National governments will need to enhance their social safety nets and invest in retraining programs to support displaced workers. EU institutions could facilitate, including by providing funds, cross-country collaboration in the area of education, technological research and development to maintain competitive edge. Additionally, private sector entities, like businesses, but also social partners could create partnerships to develop industry-specific training programs and apprenticeships, with social dialogue playing an important role. Overall the report points to a variety of policy measures that can help to address these challenges:

- Promotion of Lifelong Learning: Encouraging lifelong learning initiatives to help workers continuously update their skills.
- Promotion of Lifelong Learning: Encouraging lifelong learning initiatives to help workers continuously update their skills.

- Strategic Investment in Education and Training: Investing in continuous education and vocational training to ensure the workforce is equipped with the necessary skills to adapt to technological changes.
- Enhanced Social Safety Nets: Strengthening unemployment benefits and other social safety nets to support workers transitioning between jobs.
- Public-Private Partnerships: Fostering partnerships between governments, educational institutions, and the private sector to create targeted training programs and job placements.
- Regional Development Initiatives: Implementing policies at the local level that support economic development in regions most affected by job displacement to reduce regional disparities.
- Incentives for Innovation and Adaptation: Providing incentives for businesses to innovate and adapt to new technologies while also safeguarding jobs.
- Support for SMEs: Offering tailored support to small businesses to help them cope with technological transitions and potentially increased competition.

Ultimately, the EU's ability to navigate these challenges will depend on its capacity to coordinate actions across various levels of governance and effectively harness the strengths of all stakeholders involved. By doing so, the EU can strive to maintain its global competitiveness and ensure a more resilient, equitable labour market.

Similarly, at the global level, the EU's role as a global actor will crucially depend on its ability to coordinate actions with other global players and to continue to influence multilateral institutions.

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